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Experiences and Future Prospects of GRUCON – SLOVNAFT Cooperation in Energy Auditing Field

Miroslav Variny^{a,b}, Otto Mierka^{a,b}, Lukáš Gašparovič^c

a. GRUCON s.r.o., Nezábudková 24, 821 01 Bratislava 2, phone number +421 910 966 199, email: variny@grucon.sk

b. Ústav chemického a environmentálneho inžinierstva FCHPT STU, Radlinského 9 812 37 Bratislava 1, email: miroslav.variny@stuba.sk, otto.mierka@stuba.sk

c. SLOVNAFT a.s., Vlčie hrdlo 1, 824 12 Bratislava

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Introduction

The aim of an energy audit is traditionally seen in rationalization of energies and utilities consumption and lowering of energies and utilities related expenses. In complex industrial processes, like the refining and petrochemical ones the energies consumption often is related to process yields, product quality and sometimes also to catalyst lifetime. These factors might impose additional constraints on proposed solutions.

An extensive energy audit in SLOVNAFT refinery, performed by GRUCON, has been launched in 2009. Most of the involved auditors have been graduates, postgraduates, teaching assistants or senior lecturers in the Institute of chemical and environmental engineering at that time. Some of them, being at the same time members of GRUCON, have already had participated on several successful energy intensity decreasing projects for Slovak industries before. The extensive energy audit of the refinery is thus by right considered as the largest cooperation project between SLOVNAFT and academia by SLOVNAFT employees in the last 25 years and the auditors were often referred to as “the guys from the University”. Since then, several of the younger auditors, having acquired the energy audit participation reference, managed to get employed abroad or even in SLOVNAFT.

Others, who continue to perform at the University, strive to share the gathered practice, experience and knowledge with the undergraduates and graduates. The personal contacts and the deeper insight into the refining and petrochemical processes, gained by the auditors during energy audit execution, enables them to further cooperate with SLOVNAFT in the field of summer praxes for graduates and master theses. As an example, two graduate students elaborate their master theses in the Fluid catalytic cracking unit at present, analyzing its energy intensity and process yields variability – a topic that directly spun off from the energy audit; consulting their progress and findings with an experienced technologist in SLOVNAFT and being supervised by one of the auditors.

In this contribution we elucidate the energy auditing procedure and the subsequent steps that have led to the implementation of submitted proposals generally and on one particular example we show the characteristics of underlying analyses.

After more than five years of hard labor, we can conclude, that the energy audit itself is more or less finished, with the majority of proposed measures being in the monitoring&targeting phase or under realization. However, other proposals continue to emerge, that generally are related less to “energy efficiency” and more to “technology development” or other aspects, targeting and utilizing synergies among related or adjacent production units, or dealing with improvement of production planning system. It can be stated that by providing solid foundations for continuous improvement they represent a further step in the fruitful GRUCON-SLOVNAFT cooperation.

Auditing procedure and timeline

The energy audit of the refinery comprised more than 25 production units. The most complicated ones were analyzed separately; the smaller ones were assembled into groups (either due to their adjacent position in the refinery or to the process character similarity).

The audit itself has had following timeline:

1. Kickoff meeting;
2. Primary analysis of the process and energies and utilities consumption/production;
3. Submission of primary ideas and elucidation of their potential benefit for SLOVNAFT latest in 1 month after the kickoff meeting, common meeting yielding their approval/rejection;
4. Elaboration of approved ideas; elaboration and submission of written report;
5. Presentation of the main theses of the report latest 3 months after the kickoff meeting;
6. Defense of the report latest one month after 5.;
7. Creation of working teams aimed at implementation of audit ideas that passed the defense into projects. Regular working teams sessions, preparation of inputs for project teams. This lasted from case to case several months to two years;
8. Project manager assignment; project teams meetings. Reevaluation of projects economic feasibility. Investment project proposal preparation and its submission to the investment committee. Project proposal approval/rejection;
9. Physical implementation of economically feasible projects. Usually the available time window is constrained by the production units general revisions schedule;
10. Post-implementation phase: 3 year lasting monitoring&targeting; monthly meetings with the plant managers aimed at benefits and possible problems reporting.

As it appears from the timeline above, except for the simplest projects, the time span between idea generation and physical project implementation takes usually two years or longer. In case the project realization is bound to longer production unit shutdown (general revision for a particular production unit commonly takes place each 4 years), it may take even as long as 3 years.

The ideas generated in the audit usually fell into following categories:

- Enhanced internal condensates reuse for steam generation;
- Process control improvement – sour water stripping, amine regeneration, boiler blow down automation;
- Frequency converters application;
- Steam drives operation as backup/ their replacement by electromotors;
- Steam consumption reduction/production increase from waste heat;
- Optimization of ejectors performance;
- Preferential use of low- and middle- instead of high-pressure steam;
- Compressors part load operation optimization;
- Contributions to hydrogen production optimization;
- Contributions to steam network operation stabilization

The written audit report usually comprised two main parts: Actual state analysis based on provided operational data, P&ID schemes, project data etc. and Improvement ideas. The Actual state analysis consisted of concise process description, underlying data analysis, material and heat balances set-up and their solution; comparison among measured and calculated values. It often discussed the accuracy of process measurement devices, pointing out those providing incorrect or illogical results. It also contained separate chapter that listed all facts and findings that did not

necessary lead to energy saving ideas, but should help the technologists and operators in process control and evaluation.

The Improvement ideas part contained elaborated each approved primary idea. Usually defining the actual / historical operational state that served as base line and explaining the potential benefit generally. Additionally it tried to formulate the exact methodic for proposal benefit evaluation after it is implemented. Many of the elaborated ideas needed longer explanation, since the benefits can be best seen and understood from global point of view, whereas locally they might even increase the energy expenses. Therefore all presented ideas and their benefit calculations have been subject to additional verification by independent procedure carried out by Energy Management representatives.

The up to date implemented and monitored measures enabled the refinery to save more than 3 GWh of electric energy and more than 5 kt of steam per month. Thus they contributed to the refinery flexibility and its ability to succeed on the market.

In following subchapter we present as an example a particular idea related to Steam cracker water and steam system.

Water-and steam system valves revamp in the Steam cracker unit

A typical pyrolysis furnace simplified scheme is shown in the **Figure 1**. The pyrolysis feed passes through three feed preheat sections in the flue gas draft and then enters the pyrolysis coils in the furnace radiation section. Fuel flow to the burners is regulated to maintain the desired coil outlet temperature of the reaction mixture. Reaction mixture is cooled down from appr. 830 °C to 400 °C in the TLE heat exchanger and continues to fractionation section. Excess heat in the flue gas draft is used to preheat boiler feed water and to superheat the saturated steam produced in the TLE.

Figure 1. Water and steam system of a pyrolysis furnace in the Steam cracker unit. Legend: B – floor and wall burners; BD EX – blow down expander; BDV – blow down valve; LCV – level control valve; TCV – temperature control valve; TLE – transfer line exchanger; I. to III. – feed heating sections in the furnace convection section; IV. – pyrolysis coils in the furnace radiation section

Preheated water is evaporated in the TLE; continuous blow down is led to the blow down expander. Three regulation valves are applied in the water and steam system of each furnace: the LCV valve controls the water level in the TLE; the TCV valve controls the produced superheated 11 MPa steam temperature and the BDV valve ensures continuous blow down flow. In the Steam cracker unit, all three valves lose their regulation ability on all furnaces sooner or later.

The loss of BDV regulation ability results in higher than desired blow down flow. Since just a part of blow down heat content is recovered in the blow down expander, the excess blow down represents a substantial heat loss. Assuming a 10 t/h blow down flow (boiling water at 11.5 MPa), its expansion to 3.5 MPa (g) pressure produces 2.4 t/h saturated steam and the remaining 7.6 t/h of boiling water at 3.5 MPa (g) pressure represents heat loss of 8 GJ/h. Besides the heat loss caused by excess blow down, more boiler feedwater needs to be supplied to the furnace. This boiler feedwater is produced from cold mixed water that has to be heated from cca. 20 to 145 °C in the deaerator. In order to produce additional 7.6 t/h of boiler feedwater, additional 4 GJ/h heat has to be consumed in the deaerator.

Figure 2. Analysis of furnaces and boiler BDV regulation ability impact on blow down flow

The loss of LCV regulation ability results in higher than desired boiler feedwater flow. This in turn causes the water level in the TLE to rise. In order to avert the furnace shutdown, the operator has to increase the % of BDV opening. Thus in the end, the effect is the same as in the case of BDV regulation ability loss.

The loss of TCV regulation ability causes the produced 11 MPa steam temperature to be lower than desired. This is very unfavorable, as the steam is used in two extraction-condensing steam turbines, driving main process compressors. Lowered steam inlet temperature both worsens the steam turbines performance and causes excess erosion on the last lows of turbine blades due to increased exhaust steam wetness.

The blow down flow from furnaces and boiler can be readily obtained from the underlying analysis depicted in **Figure 2**. It is apparent that its mass flow from boiler is higher than 5 t/h most of time, often approaching 10 t/h. Furnaces exhibit even higher blow down flow, nearly always above 15 t/h. Taken together, on average at least 20 t/h of blow down is routed to blow down expander. As the total produced 11 MPa steam mass flow only rarely exceeds 200 t/h, we obtain the blow down rate of more than 10 %. However, even if considered very conservatively, the blow down rate should not exceed 5 % even for 11 MPa steam systems. As a comparison, the CSPP produces 9 MPa steam and keeps its blow down rate usually below 3.5%. Therefore, it can be concluded that the blow down rate can be decreased by at least 10 t/h in case all BDV are capable of regulation.

Figure 3. LCV and TCV opening percentage for two most problematic furnaces “F1” and “F2”. Red arrows indicate LCV regulation ability decay and steam temperature decrease trend.

The LCV and TCV opening percentage trend for two most problematic furnaces “F1” and “F2” is provided in **Figure 3**. As appears from that figure, the LCV in both cases exhibit opening percentage decrease, indicating their regulation ability decay. This is in some cases restored (see f.e. LCV opening increase from 0 to 65 % between May and August 2012 in “F2” case) as the

damaged valve undergoes the necessary repair. Especially in cases of zero or negative valve opening it is obvious that the valve does not fulfill its aim and such situation represents, besides economic losses, potential threat to given furnace operation.

Even more serious is the situation with TCV opening percentage. As is apparent from the figure, it only rarely reaches positive values, indicating that for the most of time the valve is fully (0%) or totally (-7%) closed. As a result, the 11 MPa steam temperature decreases in time, as the valves become more and more damaged and the injected water flow increases. In the case of “F1” we see a period (spring 2013) when the produced steam has been saturated or even wet (temperature of 320 °C corresponds to 11 MPa steam condensation temperature). Such furnace operation, if prolonged, may result in steam superheater failure. It can be seen that the situation seriousness has been acknowledged also by our colleagues in SLOVNAFT, since the next time the furnace is in operation (August 2013) the TCV exhibits positive opening and steam temperature reaches 480 °C, indicating that the valve has been repaired in between.

By simple heat balance, with known 11 MPa steam mass flows from furnaces and the corresponding steam temperatures, the average 11 MPa steam temperature from furnaces lies between 460 and 490 °C. Just to compare, the 11 MPa steam from boiler reaches temperature up to 535 °C. Considering the furnaces design steam temperatures, according to the combination of furnaces in operation, the produced steam temperature should vary between 500 and 510 °C.

Supposing the TCVs can be replaced by new ones that endure the severe pressure conditions longer, the mixed 11 MPa steam temperature can be increased by up to 15 °C on average. This results in 11 MPa steam consumption to condensation decrease by 2 to 3 % (1.2 to 1.8 t/h), caused by the more efficient extraction-condensing steam turbines operation at higher steam inlet temperature.

Finally, supposing that all BDVs, LCVs and TCVs are replaced by new, more durable ones, we have to recalculate the steam balance. The recalculation itself is provided in **Table 1** and is based on following principles:

- Heat available in flue gas draft of the furnaces for steam production is the same in actual and proposed operational state (thus neglecting the changes due to heat transfer rate changes in the flue gas draft)
- Produced 3.5 MPa steam heat content is to be the same in both cases (as the steam is used onsite for various purposes, unaffected by the changes performed with the regulation valves)

Table 1. Comparison of actual and proposed steam production balance

Process data	Actual state	Proposed balance	Difference
11 MPa steam to condensation, t/h	60	58.5	-1.5
3.5 MPa steam extraction GJ/h; t/h	283.5;90	290;91	+6.5; +1
3.5 MPa steam from BD EX, GJ/h, t/h	12.5;4.5	6;2	-6.5; -2.5
3.5 MPa steam total, GJ/h; t/h	296;94.5	296;93	0 ; -1.5
11 MPa steam total, GJ/h; t/h	504;150	508;149.5	+4; -0.5
11 MPa steam from furnaces, GJ/h; t/h	246;75	255;76	+9; +1
Heat consumed in furnaces flue gas draft for steam production, GJ/h	213	213	0
11 MPa steam from boiler, GJ/h; t/h	258;75	253;73.5	-5; -1.5
BFW total, GJ/h; t/h	104;170	97.5;159.5	-7.5; -10.5
Blow down, GJ/h; t/h	29.5;20	13;9	-16.5; -11
Fuel for boiler; GJ/h (90 % boiler efficiency)	240.5	236	-4.5
Mixed water import t/h	40	31.5	-9.5
Steam needed in deaerator for mixed water heating; GJ/h	26.5;9	20;7	-6.5; -2

Table 1. shows that the tangible benefit of all furnaces BDVs, LCVs and TCVs replacement is in:

- Lower fuel for boiler consumption (-4.5 GJ/h)
- Lower mixed water import (-9.5 t/h)
- Lower steam consumption in the deaerator (-2 t/h)

Saving of steam used in the deaerator may result in further fuel saving in the CSPP (as the low pressure steam used in deaerator can alternatively be imported from the CSPP); however this saving is likely to be negligible in financial terms at present, due to low liquid fuel price.

Therefore, for indicative gaseous fuel price 7 €/GJ and mixed water price 0.6 €/t the resulting benefit is approximately 300 000 €/year assuming 8000 working hours per year.

Apart from the tangible benefits, the valves replacement is expected to:

- decrease the operational expenses related to valves repair
- prolong the operational lifetime of the extraction-condensing steam turbines that suffered under low inlet steam temperature
- enable lowering of boiler feedwater pressure by 1 to 3 MPa (at present it is 17 MPa on average) that brings additional benefit in lower boiler feedwater pump power input

The BDV, LCV and TCV for the furnace “F1” are envisioned to be replaced by new ones in the first phase (in 2016). In case the experiences with the new valves are positive, other furnaces should be improved in the same way.

Ongoing and future cooperation prospects

The ongoing and future GRUCON-SLOVNAFT cooperation is envisioned to yield benefits in several areas. The first one relates to energies usage minimization and rationalization, exploiting heat integration possibilities among adjacent production units. This includes also for example minimization of unnecessary heating or cooling of semi-finished products that are utilized in further production units. Other activities target the improvement of part load operation energy intensity. Due to varying prices of liquid and gaseous fuels, there is perspective to reevaluate heat sources that satisfy certain process heat needs – in cases where the temperature level allows it, heating furnaces using fuel gas might be replaced or supplemented by steam heating, as the liquid fuel price per GJ, used in the CSPP, fell well below that of fuel gas.

Other areas of interest include f.e. participation of the auditors in investment projects aimed at C2 and higher HCs recovery from refinery fuel gases and their assistance as expert consultants and referees in various benchmarking studies.

The auditors also dealt with energies and media consumption planning model for the whole SLOVNAFT and proposed changes that are supposed to make the planning process more accurate and efficient. A similar procedure can be performed also for yield structures and might further contribute to production planning process efficiency.

Conclusions

The energy audit performed by GRUCON in SLOVNAFT refinery is most probably one of the most important cooperation projects of people from academia and praxis in recent years. It contributed to its flexibility and reduced its own energetic consumption. Such attitude to operational costs is necessary for any refinery that is to survive the increasingly difficult conditions on the market.

It can be concluded that the existing substantial cooperation potential is likely to result not only in financial benefits, but also in further experiences and expertise acquisition that the auditors

intend to utilize in teaching process improvement. Last, but not least, it can further enhance and contribute to interesting topics for future summer praxes and diploma theses, thereby strengthening the practically oriented cooperation between the academia and SLOVNAFT.

List of symbols and abbreviations used

B	floor and wall burners
BD EX	blow down expander
BDV	blow down valve
CSPP	combined steam and power plant
F	furnace
HC	hydrocarbon
LCV	level control valve
PU	production unit
TCV	temperature control valve
TLE	transfer line exchanger

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